

Thesis Summary

“ENABLING FIRMS IN THE MARCHE REGION TO UNDERSTAND BLOCKCHAIN FOR SUPPLY CHAIN TRACEABILITY THROUGH A TRIPLE HELIX APPROACH”

Niccolò Testi

University of Macerata, Italy

n.testi@unimc.it

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/niccolo-testi/>

Contents

Conclusions	1
<i>Summary of the findings</i>	2
<i>Final considerations on the usefulness of blockchain for traceability of Made in Italy products</i>	8
<i>Managerial implications</i>	11
<i>Policy implications</i>	11
<i>Future research</i>	11

Conclusions

This Thesis focuses on the application of BCT in firms, particularly SMEs, of the Marche Region to explore how it can enhance their competitiveness in both domestic and international markets.

Recent studies have analysed the potential of BCT in various fields beyond cryptocurrency. BCT is particularly relevant for supply chain traceability, allowing firms to store and share immutable product traceability data, and thus enhancing transparency, building trust, identifying counterfeit products, and increasing consumer trust and loyalty.

BCT can play a significant role in supply chains of Made in Italy products by valorising them, protecting them from counterfeiting, and combating "Italian-sounding". However, despite its potential benefits, there is still a gap between theoretical advantages and empirical evidence of BCT's effectiveness. Several high-profile blockchain projects have faced challenges or failed, reflecting difficulties in practical implementation.

This Thesis intends to bridge this gap by providing empirical evidence from real BCT implementations in Italian supply chains.

The objective is to understand the advantages and challenges of the potential adoption of BCT for supply chain traceability in SMEs of the Made in Italy in the Marche region.

The research adopts a strong empirical approach, employing qualitative methodologies like interviews and surveys to gather real-world evidence. The Thesis also aims to cover the technical, economic, and legal aspects of BCT adoption through an interdisciplinary approach, offering practical, evidence-based insights for managers and policymakers in the Marche region.

Summary of the findings

Chapter I of the Thesis provides a comprehensive introduction to BCT, explaining its functionality, utility, and how it compares with centralized databases. It delves into the specifics of blockchain-enabled tools such as smart contracts, decentralized applications, and non-fungible tokens, highlighting their features and limitations. A key focus of the chapter is the exploration of the conditions under which blockchain databases are preferred over centralized ones, noting that blockchains are often adopted to eliminate the need for trust and intermediaries in data sharing between stakeholders.

However, the chapter reveals a paradox in this adoption: while blockchain is designed to remove the need for trust, the validity of data input by external sources (oracles) often requires pre-existing trust and possibly trusted intermediaries for verification.

Additionally, the chapter addresses one of the major limitations of BCT, which is its lack of scalability. This issue is explored within the context of the BCT trilemma, which impacts all blockchains. The scalability limitations of BCT are addressed through various solutions, each compromising trust to some extent.

Off-chain storage, where data is stored outside the blockchain and only hashes are kept on-chain, increases scalability but raises concerns about data access and centralization. The most studied and used consensus algorithms like PoW, PoS, and PoA offer trade-offs between scalability, decentralization, and security. For example, PoW ensures security and decentralization but limits scalability, while PoS and PoA offer greater scalability at the expense of decentralization and security.

Blockchain architectures, classified as permissionless (public), permissioned (private, consortium), also balance scalability, control, and privacy. Permissionless blockchains, like Bitcoin, are decentralized and secure but less scalable. In contrast, permissioned blockchains are more scalable but less decentralized and secure, with consortium blockchains offering a middle ground.

Hybrid architectures, involving multiple interconnected blockchains, propose a solution for scalability and decentralization but face interoperability challenges. The overall power dynamics within these networks can shift, potentially centralizing initially decentralized structures.

All these solutions tend to reintroduce elements of centralization and the need for intermediaries, thus challenging the fundamental principles of BCT.

Chapter II reviews the topic of BCT for supply chain traceability, focusing on its business and management implications.

The study's review of academic literature highlights a growing interest in this field, particularly in the agri-food and pharmaceutical sectors due to concerns over food contamination and counterfeit medicines.

Through the literature review, two main themes are identified.

The first theme regards the benefits of using BCT in supply chains, which are categorized into three sub-themes: the enhancement of transparency and its positive effect on trust among supply chain stakeholders; the increase in consumer trust regarding the product's originality and safety; the improvement in supply chain effectiveness, resilience, performance, and sustainability.

The second theme explores the drivers and barriers to firms' intention to adopt BCT for supply chain traceability. While BCT is desired for enhancing data transparency and thereby improving trust and accountability in supply chains, compliance with regulations, fraud detection, and increasing resilience, performance, and sustainability, significant barriers to its adoption include a lack of digital knowledge, insufficient resources, unclear regulations, governance challenges, privacy concerns, and technical issues of blockchains. Consumer preference for products traced with BCT and their willingness to pay a premium are potential income sources, but evidence on this is scarce and conflicting.

The main advantage of BCT-enabled traceability over centralized systems could be its role in enabling trust among supply chain stakeholders, which is a significant driver for its adoption. However, the increased transparency could also lead to concerns about data confidentiality.

Permissioned blockchains, offering differentiated access rights, have been suggested to protect sensitive information, but their effectiveness and governance challenges are still to be fully understood. Moreover, permissioned blockchains might not effectively enable trust due to their lower decentralization, potentially making them less desirable than centralized databases.

Further, the reliability of data uploaded to a blockchain is a critical concern. The information can be inaccurate due to human error or manipulation before being uploaded. Using IoT devices for automatic data collection and uploading has been proposed to enhance reliability, but further research is needed on how to prevent the manipulation of these devices by malicious actors.

Finally, the chapter highlights that while BCT promises to address certain problems of centralized supply chain traceability systems, particularly the issue of lack of trust among stakeholders, there remains a notable gap in empirical evidence demonstrating the benefits of BCT for supply chain traceability, particularly when weighing against the costs and risks involved. Indeed, more than half of the articles reviewed are conceptual, focusing on the potential advantages and disadvantages of BCT from a theoretical perspective.

Empirical research is limited and does not compare BCT with centralized supply chain traceability solutions. This creates uncertainty about the actual value of BCT compared to its implementation costs and existing solutions.

While some studies indicate cost reduction and real-time monitoring as benefits of BCT, it's unclear if these outcomes are exclusive to BCT or achievable with existing centralized solutions too.

Additionally, the indirect benefits of BCT, such as incentivizing digitalization and the use of smart contracts for automation, could be achieved without BCT.

Recognising both the potential of BCT applied to supply chain traceability for firms of the Made in Italy and the lack of evidence on the topic, the first study of **Chapter III** focuses on collecting firsthand data through expert interviews with managerial and technical staff from Italian SMEs using BCT for supply chain traceability of Made in Italy products and tech companies providing this technology.

The interviews confirm that BCT enhances transparency and accountability in supply chains, leading to increased trust among stakeholders. However, in cases where trust is already established, BCT may not add significant value, especially in shorter food supply chains.

BCT's role in anti-counterfeiting is beneficial for protecting the Made in Italy brand and involves stakeholders in verifying product originality.

Additionally, transparency through BCT can lead to increased revenues, as consumers value and are willing to pay more for products with transparent traceability.

A key application of BCT in this context is for B2C marketing, allowing SMEs to tell the story of their products, enhancing consumer perception of the reliability and quality of their Made in Italy products.

The assumption behind this application is backed by some studies that found a positive effect of BCT-enabled traceability on consumers' purchasing intentions and willingness to pay a premium. However, depending on how the researchers conducting these surveys and experiments described the application of BCT for supply chain traceability to participants in their studies, their perception could have been biased into considering only the advantages and not the limitations of BCT-enabled traceability.

Finally, findings from this study on the use of BCT for supply chain traceability in firms of the Made in Italy evidenced that the use of smart contracts for storing traceability event hashes and

Challenges in the adoption of BCT include a lack of clear legal frameworks, standardization issues, and insufficient knowledge about BCT among companies. Effective communication about the benefits of BCT is crucial for its adoption. NFTs are not widely used due to their negative reputation and technical constraints.

Technical solutions involve using off-chain storage for scalability and data confidentiality but raises concerns about centralization and control by data managers and exposes the stakeholders to the risk of data loss.

Different blockchain architectures, like consortium and public blockchains, offer various advantages, with some providers using a hybrid approach for better transparency and cost predictability. Third-generation public blockchains are used for more scalability but at the expense of decentralisation and security of the blockchain network.

Risks of data unreliability arise from human error, fraudulent manipulation, and the potential for displaying false information. Providers recommend using IoT for automatic data collection to minimize human intervention errors.

The notarization of the producer's declaration is a common practice, but it doesn't guarantee the data's reliability before blockchain entry. Some solutions allow supply chain partners to autonomously upload data using smart contracts, enhancing accountability but not ensuring reliability. Italian adopters predominantly use the producer's declaration method, influenced by factors like cultural barriers and a focus on marketing.

Risks also emerge from the use of centralized apps to display traceability information, prompting some providers to adopt DApps for greater trustworthiness, as these run on public blockchains and offer open-source, immutable code.

The chapter provides managerial implications, guiding SMEs in understanding if they need a BCT solution and which solution fits their needs.

Firms should assess the trust among stakeholders in their supply chains. If trust is lacking, BCT is useful for data sharing among multiple parties without relying on a trusted third party for data handling. This focus on trust enhancement through BCT is particularly leveraged for B2C marketing purposes.

Further, the second study of the chapter investigates through a survey the opinions of Italian adopters on the usefulness of BCT for supply chain traceability, particularly in B2C marketing contexts. The respondents, primarily from micro-sized companies, were from sectors emblematic of the Made in Italy, like agri-food, furniture, and fashion.

The survey results indicate that most adopters perceive BCT as positively influencing customer trust, brand awareness, and the willingness of customers to pay a premium for BCT-traced products, which are areas of B2C marketing related to brand awareness and loyalty. However, this positive influence seemed to not significantly impact the number of products sold.

The findings suggest that while BCT positively affects areas related to B2C marketing, its influence on trust among supply chain partners and efficiency is less pronounced.

Additional benefits noted were promoting genuine Italian products, increasing transparency, and aiding in compliance with future digital product passport legislation.

Interestingly, only a minority of adopter have direct access to performance data of the BCT service, with some reliant on providers for data access. This raises concerns about the reliability of data and the adopters' capacity to assess the impact of BCT on their business accurately.

Only two respondents actively use performance data for business decision-making, suggesting a lack of awareness or accessibility of crucial data.

Looking ahead, most respondents intend to continue using BCT services for traceability, driven by customer demand and upcoming legislation. However, the continuation for some is contingent on cost factors, indicating that while BCT is seen as beneficial, its practical application and long-term viability are still being evaluated by these firms.

This cautious approach reflects a broader need for understanding BCT's tangible benefits and aligning them with business goals and regulatory requirements.

Chapter IV explores the dynamic capabilities (DCs) as enablers, and legal challenges as barriers, to the adoption of BCT for supply chain traceability in Italy.

The first study presented in the chapter contributes to understanding the intersection between DCs and BCT adoption of BCT for supply chain traceability in Italian firms. The research applies the DCs theory and, through interviews with six Italian firms of the Made in Italy that use BCT in their supply chain, the study reveals how these companies learned about and adopted BCT and how they adapted their operations to the new technology.

The findings show that most firms were introduced to BCT through external sources like seminars, webinars, or consultants, indicating a reliance on external expertise for identifying technological opportunities.

In seizing these opportunities, firms predominantly leaned on consultants to choose appropriate BCT providers.

Consultants emerge as key facilitators in the adoption process, acting as knowledge brokers and aiding in technology integration. However, this reliance also suggests a potential lack of in-house understanding of BCT and its applications. While consultants can provide valuable guidance, firms should be cautious of over-reliance, especially considering potential conflicts of interest.

Interestingly, the educational background of the firms' owners or CEOs appears to play a positive role in the successful adoption of BCT. Higher education levels, combined with an openness to innovation, seem to positively influence BCT adoption.

As for the phase of transforming to adapt to BCT, no significant transformation of internal capabilities or processes was required for BCT use, mainly due to BCT providers' involvement in implementation.

The second part of the chapter discusses the legal challenges around BCT as potential barriers to its implementation and diffusion in firms, with a focus on BCT for supply chain traceability.

The exploration of BCT, smart contracts, and NFTs across Europe, Italy, and the Marche Region reveals a legal framework grappling with the integration of BCT.

The primary challenge is aligning BCT with existing laws, particularly the GDPR in the EU. The GDPR's emphasis on data privacy clashes with the immutable and decentralized nature of blockchains, leading to significant challenges in legal compliance. The GDPR's challenges for BCT include its principles of the right to erasure and data minimization, which conflict with blockchain's inherent features like data immutability. Possible solutions include permissioned blockchains, which offer a more controlled environment conducive to GDPR compliance, and off-chain storage, allowing for data modification or deletion while maintaining blockchain benefits.

At the EU level, there is a lack of specific legal frameworks for BCT, with the EC mainly focusing on fostering a pro-innovation environment while ensuring legal certainty. The EC's European Blockchain Regulatory Sandbox is an example of this approach, supporting

projects to increase legal clarity for BCT innovations, including public sector applications on the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure.

In Italy, the legislation's definition of DLTs and smart contracts under DL 135/2018 offers some regulatory clarity but also reveals gaps, particularly in addressing permissioned DLTs where data modification is possible.

Regarding smart contracts, Italy's legal system has attempted to define them broadly, but this generic approach may be ineffective in practical legal contexts.

The legal landscape for NFTs remains ambiguous, with ongoing debates about their classification under existing legal categories. European Parliament resolutions and the EC's proposed regulation on crypto-assets markets address DLT but lack specificity regarding NFTs.

In terms of traceability, particularly in the food sector, the EU's regulations mandate traceability requirements, but the integration of BCT into these systems poses legal and technical challenges. BCT could enhance traceability but requires legal and digitalization strategies to align with food law.

Overall, the legal challenges of BCT in Europe, Italy, and the Marche Region reflect a need for more precise legal guidelines and frameworks. This evolving legal landscape calls for collaboration among firms, policymakers, legislators, and researchers to navigate and address the complexities of integrating blockchain into existing legal structures.

Chapter V, recognising that knowledge on the use of BCT for supply chain traceability in Italian firms is scarce and heavily influenced by providers and consultants, argues that TH actors and innovation intermediaries should be involved in the diffusion of knowledge on BCT in firms of the Marche region to foster its adoption.

The study explores the application of a Triple TH model to enhance the understanding and adoption of BCT among the other I4.0 technologies, in firms of the Marche region. This TH approach, which emphasizes collaboration among academia, government, and industry, emerges as a framework to address the challenges that SMEs face in integrating I4.0 technologies, BCT included.

The research methodology combines a literature review, an analysis of the regional context and policies, and a targeted survey of innovative local firms.

The research findings highlight a general awareness of BCT among firms in the Marche Region, but its actual implementation remains limited. Also, firms value networking activities with academia and other firms that are already utilizing I4.0 technologies. Moreover, the firms recognize the importance of governmental support in terms of funding and incentives for implementing I4.0 technologies.

The proposed TH model for the Marche region positions innovation intermediaries, such as DIHs, PID, Competence Centers, Fondazione Cluster Marche, and i-Labs, at the centre of the TH collaboration. These intermediaries facilitate the flow of knowledge and foster collaborative initiatives between academia, government, and industry. Also, innovation intermediaries, and DIH specifically, connect regional firms with broader European networks for gaining access to a wider array of knowledge and best practices in the field of I4.0 technologies.

One key observation from the survey is the underutilization of DIHs by the firms, despite their potential role as connectors, which indicates a possible gap in awareness or accessibility regarding the services offered by DIHs. To address this, the study suggests that both policymakers and DIHs need to enhance the visibility and perceived value of DIHs among regional firms. For instance, organizing events and workshops that bring together firms, technology providers, and other European stakeholders could demonstrate the practical benefits of engaging with DIHs.

Another significant aspect highlighted by the study is the role of the S3 in fostering the adoption of I4.0 technologies in the region. The involvement of key intermediaries in the implementation of the S3 is crucial for its success. This involvement can facilitate the dissemination of I4.0 technologies and support the region's economic development through technological innovation.

Finally, the chapter argues about the necessity for TH actors to adopt a forward-looking vision that aligns with the evolving landscape of urban digitalization, by integrating BCT within smart cities, specifically for enhancing supply chain traceability. The integration of BCT in smart cities is a transformative step towards ensuring transparency, efficiency, and security in urban management systems. Such integration can significantly enhance the management of supply chains, offering real-time tracking, improved decision-making, and enhanced transparency.

The IoT facilitates the connection and data exchange among various entities both in I4.0 and smart city, paving the way for real-time tracking and management of goods.

When combined with BCT, it can enhance food supply chain traceability, a critical aspect in urban settings. This combination ensures data integrity and offers real-time quality indicators essential for maintaining food safety standards.

However, integrating BCT in smart cities for supply chain traceability is not without challenges.

Technical considerations include choosing the appropriate type of blockchain, with consortium blockchains emerging as a suitable choice for smart city governance due to their balance between scalability, efficiency, and collaborative governance.

The choice of consensus algorithm is also crucial, with PoA being proposed for its suitability in semi-centralized systems like smart cities.

Also, the early development stage of both BCT and smart cities necessitates considerable research and development efforts, which in turn require a collaborative effort involving various stakeholders.

The TH model, promoting cooperation between government, academia, and industry, can play an important role in facilitating this integration.

Final considerations on the usefulness of blockchain for traceability of Made in Italy products

BCT, invented in 2008, was designed to facilitate P2P exchanges of value across network nodes without relying on intermediaries like banks to confirm transaction accuracy and guarantee their permanence and immutability once registered. This technology shifts trust from interpersonal relationships to the deterministic outcomes of the blockchain's

protocol and the immutability of transactions stored on the blockchain. Blockchains, thus, eliminate the need for both interpersonal trust among peers exchanging value and intermediaries acting as trusted third parties.

An interesting feature of blockchains is their ability to store strings of text within P2P transactions. This capability paves the way for using blockchains to store data in a manner that is immutable and transparent. Consequently, since 2015, BCT has been proposed as a potential solution to foster trust-less data exchanges in many sectors plagued by trust deficits among parties. The applications proposed for BCT are so diverse and far from its original cryptocurrency application, that BCT has been considered as a solution seeking problems to solve.

In recent years, there has been increasing academic interest in BCT as a means to enhance transparency in supply chains. The idea is for companies to upload traceability data about their products onto a blockchain, making this information immutable and accessible to stakeholders, thereby addressing the issues of information asymmetry and lack of transparency typical of centralized traceability systems. This approach aims to enable trust building in supply chains, especially in light of growing consumer and regulatory concerns about frauds exploiting the opacity of increasingly globalized and complex supply chains. The expectation is that BCT would mitigate issues related to the lack of transparency and trust in centralized supply chain traceability systems by making such data immutable and visible to all supply chain stakeholders, including partners, certifiers, authorities, and customers, without needing a third party to store and validate this information.

However, in the context of BCT-enabled supply chain traceability, two primary issues emerge.

Firstly, the traceability data stored on the blockchain are sourced from oracles like supply chain partners, who might provide inaccurate data due to error or deceit. Therefore, these oracles need to be reliable. Additionally, intermediaries as trusted third parties may still be required to verify the accuracy of the data. This situation creates a paradox in BCT adoption for supply chains: while BCT is sought to eliminate the need for trust and intermediaries, it paradoxically requires pre-existing trust among supply chain partners and the involvement of intermediaries for its implementation. However, if trust already exists among partners or reliable third parties are available to validate the traceability data, then the necessity for BCT becomes questionable.

Secondly, blockchains face scalability challenges, making it impractical to store large volumes of data. Proposed solutions like off-chain storage, specific consensus algorithms, and permissioned blockchains reintroduce a degree of centralization in a system initially designed to be decentralized, potentially compromising the blockchain network's security and the foundational BCT principle of trust elimination.

The question then arises: can BCT truly meet the expectations set for it in supply chain traceability? The lack of empirical studies leaves this answer uncertain, though scepticism regarding BCT's ability to fully eliminate the need for trust is reasonable.

While BCT might not completely remove the need for trust in supply chains, it has been suggested as a mechanism for fostering trust in the traceability of Made in Italy products by making data immutable and accessible to stakeholders.

Italian BCT service providers for supply chain traceability predominantly use off-chain storage. This approach poses risks such as data loss and may undermine stakeholder confidence in the perpetual availability and auditability of traceability data. Therefore, BCT's role in enhancing trust in supply chains might be limited.

Furthermore, the prevalent practice of using centralized apps by providers to display traceability data introduces risks of incorrect data presentation, either intentionally by providers or due to hacking. Utilizing DApps could potentially mitigate this issue.

Third-generation public blockchains are frequently employed in BCT services for tracing Made in Italy products to improve scalability. However, this choice is contentious as such blockchains use consensus algorithms like Proof of Stake (PoS) and Proof of Authority (PoA), which, while enhancing scalability, reduce decentralization and security. This reduction in security could facilitate hacker attacks.

Additionally, the motivation for Italian adopters to utilize BCT in supply chain traceability primarily revolves around its use as a B2C marketing tool. The underlying assumption is that consumers prefer and are willing to pay more for BCT-traced products. Although some surveys and experimental evidence support this assumption, participant bias cannot be ruled out if only the benefits and not the limitations of BCT-enabled traceability were highlighted.

Further, empirical evidence presented in Chapter III shows that Italian firms adopting BCT in their supply chains heavily depend on consultants and providers for knowing and implementing BCT. There is a concern that these firms may not be fully informed about BCT's limitations in enhancing supply chain trust, given the potential conflict of interest where consultants and providers might emphasize benefits over drawbacks.

Interestingly, while adopters recognize B2C marketing advantages of using BCT for supply chain traceability, many lack direct access to performance data of the blockchain service and do not use this data for business decision-making. This could suggest either an inability to interpret the data or its irrelevance. Despite these challenges, most adopters plan to continue using BCT services in the foreseeable future.

Finally, the absence of clear legal frameworks at European, Italian, and regional levels in Marche presents additional risks for firms using BCT, smart contracts, and NFTs.

Therefore, the Thesis advocates for a Triple Helix (TH) approach in the Marche Region to enhance local firms' understanding of BCT for supply chain traceability. This approach could diminish the disproportionate influence of consultants and providers and offer unbiased knowledge to firms.

In conclusion, while BCT seems to bring opportunities for enhancing trust and transparency in supply chains, its effective implementation requires careful consideration of its limitations, scalability issues, and the balance between decentralization and security. This makes informed decision-making, clear legal frameworks, and collaborative TH approaches crucial in the adoption of BCT.

Managerial implications

This thesis offers businesses detailed insights into BCT for supply chain traceability, aiding them in strategic decision-making.

The primary recommendation is for SMEs with limited budgets for digital innovation to first focus on digitalizing their supply chains and adopting proven Industry 4.0 technologies, such as RFID for tracing or QR codes and NFCs on product labels for consumer information access, before considering BCT. This is due to the current lack of conclusive evidence on the benefits of BCT adoption.

However, if firms identify BCT as a potential solution for enhancing trust among stakeholders in data management, they should seek unbiased information from sources like public universities, government institutions, innovation intermediaries, and BCT adopters.

Firms must also consider the inherent trade-offs in blockchain technology, known as the BCT trilemma: the impossibility of achieving scalability, decentralization, and security simultaneously. Therefore, if a proposed blockchain service emphasizes scalability, firms should be aware that it may compromise decentralization and security, potentially failing to build trust among stakeholders.

After implementing BCT, firms should insist on getting direct access to performance data from their blockchain service provider, so that they can assess the service's effectiveness at any moment.

Additionally, understanding the legal implications of using BCT is crucial. Firms should consider the type of data being stored on blockchains, whether it's on-chain or off-chain, and the nature of the blockchain they want to use (e.g., permissionless or permissioned, private or consortium, hybrid), as these factors influence data management responsibilities and compliance requirements.

Policy implications

Regarding policy implications, the study highlights the absence of clear legal frameworks for using BCT in supply chain traceability.

Policymakers are encouraged to establish a regulatory environment that is adaptable enough to foster experimentation with BCT-based applications.

This approach should promote collaborative projects that bring together various academic and non-academic stakeholders, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and the development of effective market and societal solutions. Governmental support through public funding and institutional backing can expedite this process.

Alongside these regulatory efforts, governments should also focus on educating and enhancing citizens' and firms' understanding of BCT and its application in supply chain traceability.

Future research

Research on BCT is still at an early stage and the supposed benefits and costs of this innovative technology, when applied to supply chain traceability, are yet to be proven.

This Thesis provides some interesting insights based on empirical qualitative studies. However, these are based on the few firms that accepted to be interviewed or surveyed, thus, the results cannot be generalised.

Future research should adopt an interdisciplinary and empirical approach involving technical and socio-economic perspectives to analyse more case studies of real long-term applications of BCT for supply chain traceability.

As Compagnucci et al. (2022) state, the challenges for the application of BCT to supply chains are multifaceted and complex and necessitate a comprehensive approach that considers technical, operational, regulatory, and collaborative aspects to successfully leverage BCT in supply chain management and beyond.

First, benchmarking of the costs and benefits of using BCT compared to other existing centralised software for supply chain traceability is needed, also considering the technical aspects of the different BCT solutions that firms could use. This benchmarking should be based on real implementations of BCT in firms, possibly on longitudinal case studies to follow the implementation of BCT in firms and the associated costs and benefits throughout time. This would give companies relevant insights to understand the profitability of the different blockchain solutions and what profit margin they need to cover the costs of implementing BCT in their supply chain.

Secondly, research must explore how the absence of clear legal frameworks affects the adoption of BCT for supply chain traceability, the use of smart contracts, and NFTs. This should include a comparative analysis across different countries to understand the broader regulatory impact.

Finally, there is a need to rigorously test the assumption that consumers prefer and are willing to pay more for BCT-traced Made in Italy products. While existing studies suggest this assumption may be true, the lack of rigour and transparency in their methodology calls for caution. Future studies should offer participants a comprehensive and balanced understanding of BCT, including both its potential and limitations, so that participant responses are not skewed by biases in the information provided.